

switching between two limiting steady states of high and low iodide ion concentrations. Iodine is produced by a radical process when the iodide ion concentration is low and consumed at high iodide ion concentration. Iodine production involves the iodine dioxide oxidation of manganese(II) with subsequent rapid reduction by H_2O_2 and the gross reaction is represented by

Iodine is consumed by the organic substrate like acetoacetic ester giving iodo-derivatives.

Iodous acid is believed to play a role similar to that of bromous acid in Belousov-Zhabotinskii reaction. For radical production leading to iodine we have the principal fate of iodous acid as (1)

and for high iodide ion concentration (the conditions prevailing during iodine consumption) the principal fate of iodous acid is (2)

Switching is anticipated to occur whenever the iodide ion concentration passes through the value

$$[I^-] = \frac{k_1}{k_2} [IO_2^-]$$

For $[I^-]$ less than this value, production of iodine will dominate leading to an autocatalytic rise in iodous acid concentration limited by the second order disproportionation of this species ($2HIO_2 \rightarrow HIO_3 + HIO$). For $[I^-]$ greater than this value, iodine consumption dominates and the iodous acid concentration is maintained low.

In the present studies, as both acetone and ethyl alcohol are iodine consumers, it can be reasonably expected that the oscillation period will more and more decrease when concentration of acetone or ethyl alcohol is increased because of an increase in iodine consumption rate. Again, H_2O_2 and KIO_3 are consumed more in each cycle and hence the number of possible oscillations as also the total time of oscillation will decrease as acetone (or ethyl alcohol) concentration is increased. The permanent blue colour also appears in a shorter time as the whole process is hastened. Further studies are obviously necessary for quantitative elucidation.

References

1. T. S. BRIGGS and W. C. RAUSCHER, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1973, 50, 496.
2. D. O. COOKE, *J. C. S. Chem. Commun.*, 1976, 27.
3. A. K. DUTT and R. S. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 546.
4. D. O. COOKE, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1976, 4, 329.
5. D. O. COOKE, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1979, 37, 259.
6. D. O. COOKE, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1980, 12, 671.
7. P. DEKEPPER and I. R. EPSTEIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 104, 49.
8. R. M. NOYES and S. D. FURROW, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 104, 45.

A Recalculation of pK_1 and pK_2 of *o*-Phthalic Acid at a Number of Temperatures

A. K. SINGH and J. C. GHOSH*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

Manuscript received 12 April 1982, revised 28 January 1983, accepted 23 April 1983

PRASAD¹ has shown that Davies equation² does not correctly represent the activity coefficient γ_1 of an ion but equation (1), which he called modified Davies equation, does.

$$\log \gamma_1 = -\frac{Az_1^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + \beta_1 \mu \quad \dots (1)$$

In equation (1) he assumed that, (i) β_1 is additive, and (ii) β_1 is reasonably independent of the composition of ionic atmosphere in dilute solutions, provided its composition is not drastically changed.

The pK_1 and pK_2 values of *o*-phthalic acid in aqueous solution from 273.15 to 333.15 K in steps of 5 K as determined by Hamer, Pinching and Acree³ and Hamer and Acree⁴, respectively, from cells without liquid junction are taken to be the most accurate values. In the present work we have recalculated pK_1 and pK_2 of *o*-phthalic acid using the data of Hamer and coworkers and the modified Davies equation to show that the assumptions underlying this equation are reasonably correct. The use of this equation considerably simplifies the calculation and gives pK_1 and pK_2 values of comparable accuracy.

By using four series of solutions having varying values of $m_1 : m_2 : m_3$ in cell (C-1) over $\mu = 0.002$ to 0.45 mol kg^{-1} , Hamer and Acree determined pK_2 .
 (Pd)H₂ | KHPH, K₂Ph, KCl, AgCl | Ag (C-1)
 | m₁ m₂ m₃ |

The e.m.f. of cell (C-1) and the ionic strength of cell solutions are given by equations (2) and (3), respectively.

$$E = E^0 - k \log m_H \cdot m_{Cl} - k \log \gamma_H \cdot \gamma_{Cl} \quad \dots (2)$$

where, $k = \frac{2.3026 RT}{F}$ and $E^0 = E_{Ag^+/Ag, Cl^-, Cl^-}$.

$$\mu = m_1 + 3m_2 + m_3 + 2m_H \quad (3)$$

Use of modified Davies equation (1) in equation (2) gives equation (4), which in turn gives m_H by an iterative procedure, since the values of A , E^0 and k are known from literature⁶⁻⁸ and Hamer and Acree⁵ found that E^0 of cells (C-2) and (C-3) are identical over 273.15 to 333.15 K.

The values of β obtained⁹ with cell (C-2) can be used in equation (4), if the assumptions of modified Davies equation be correct.

NOTES

TABLE 1— pK_2 OF *o*-PHTHALIC ACID

Temp. K	Recalculated values of pK_2					pK_2 Hamer and Acree's value	
	Series A	Series B	Series C	Series D	Statistically, taking all the points together		Graphically, taking all the points together
278.15	5.4179	5.4149	5.4158	5.4218	5.418 ± 0.0015	5.417	5.4180 ± 0.0008
283.15	5.4087	5.4092	5.4101	5.4167	5.411 ± 0.0034	5.409	5.4096 ± 0.0009
288.15	5.4037	5.4047	5.4055	5.4152	5.407 ± 0.0023	5.405	5.4052 ± 0.0009
293.15	5.4038	5.4046	5.4050	5.4115	5.406 ± 0.0056	5.405	5.4048 ± 0.0008
298.15	5.4107	5.4106	5.4166	5.4148	5.411 ± 0.0016	5.410	5.4183 ± 0.0008
303.15	5.4181	5.4187	5.4214	5.3997	5.415 ± 0.0011	5.418	5.4157 ± 0.0009
308.15	5.4243	5.4280	5.4200	5.4329	5.429 ± 0.0026	5.428	5.4271 ± 0.0010
313.15	5.4431	5.4435	5.4449	5.4481	5.445 ± 0.0025	5.443	5.4424 ± 0.0008
318.15	5.4599	5.4609	5.4619	5.4675	5.463 ± 0.0025	5.461	5.4617 ± 0.0008
323.15	5.4818	5.4827	5.4835	5.4906	5.485 ± 0.0014	5.483	5.4849 ± 0.0009

TABLE 2— pK_1 OF *o*-PHTHALIC ACID

Temp. K	Recalculated values of pK_1				pK_1 Hamer, Pinching and Acree's value	
	Series I	Series II	Series V	Statistically, taking all the points together		Graphically, taking all the points together
278.15	2.9231	2.9242	2.9226	2.9233 ± 0.0005	2.923	2.9273 ± 0.0010
283.15	2.9281	2.9308	2.9303	2.9297 ± 0.0007	2.929	2.9314 ± 0.0008
288.15	2.9336	2.9351	2.9344	2.9344 ± 0.0003	2.934	2.9367 ± 0.0006
293.15	2.9423	2.9424	2.9427	2.9425 ± 0.0004	2.942	2.9429 ± 0.0006
298.15	2.9543	2.9548	2.9578	2.956 ± 0.0025	2.955	2.9496 ± 0.0005
303.15	2.9625	2.9631	2.9614	2.9623 ± 0.0009	2.963	2.9580 ± 0.0008
308.15	2.9697	2.9657	2.9670	2.968 ± 0.0021	2.967	2.9672 ± 0.0010
313.15	2.9806	2.9771	2.9799	2.9792 ± 0.0008	2.979	2.9776 ± 0.0007
318.15	2.9858	2.9861	2.9853	2.9857 ± 0.0004	2.986	2.9884 ± 0.0008
323.15	2.9975	2.9962	2.9953	2.9963 ± 0.0005	2.997	3.0007 ± 0.0008

$$E - \frac{k \cdot 2A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} + k \log m_H \cdot m_{Cl} = E^0 - k \beta \mu \quad \dots (4)$$

As, $m_{HPh} = m_1 - m_H$
 $m_{Ph} = m_2 + m_H$

and $K_2 = \frac{m_H \cdot m_{Ph}}{m_{HPh}} \cdot \frac{\gamma_H \cdot \gamma_{Ph}}{\gamma_{HPh}}$

So, $\log K_{A(2)} - \frac{4A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_2 - \beta_2 \mu \quad \dots (5)$

where, $K_{A(2)} = \frac{m_H \cdot m_{Ph}}{m_{HPh}}$ and $\beta_2 = (\beta_H + \beta_{Ph} - \beta_{HPh})$.

Plots of L.H.S. of equation (5) against μ , at all the temperatures were found to be linear. The intercepts of the lines at $\mu=0$ gave $\log K_2$ and the slopes gave β_2 .

The values of pK_2 thus found graphically as well as by least square analysis, together with the values of Hamer and Acree are recorded in Table 1.

The recalculations have been confined to $\mu=0.18$ mol kg⁻¹, since modified Davies equation is found to be generally valid upto $\mu=0.1$ mol kg⁻¹ and sometimes upto $\mu=0.2$ mol kg⁻¹.

To determine pK_1 , Hamer, Pinching and Acree used cell (C-4) and five series of solutions having varying values of $m_4 : m_5 : m_6$ and μ from 0.002 to 0.037 mol kg⁻¹.

The e.m.f. of cell (C-4) also is given by equation (2).

In the cell solution the following equilibria will hold

From the above, by identity

$$m_{H_2Ph} + m_H = m_4 + m_{Ph} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$m_{HPh} + 2m_{Ph} = m_5 + m_H \quad \dots (7)$$

$$m_4 + m_5 = m_{H_2Ph} + m_{HPh} + m_{Ph} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\mu = m_5 + m_6 + m_H, \text{ since } m_{Ph} \text{ is negligible} \quad \dots (9)$$

First we start with $\mu = m_5 + m_4$ and by an iterative procedure using equations (4), (5) and (7), we find m_H and μ . Equations (6), (7) and (8) then enable us to find m_{HPh} , m_{H_2Ph} and m_{Ph} .

Now, $\log K_{A(1)} - \frac{2A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = \log K_1 - \beta_1 \mu \quad \dots (10)$

where, $K_{A(1)} = \frac{m_H \cdot m_{HPh}}{m_{H_2Ph}}$

$$K_1 = \frac{m_H \cdot m_{HPh}}{m_{H_2Ph}} \cdot \frac{\gamma_H \cdot \gamma_{HPh}}{m_{H_2Ph}}$$

and $\beta_1 = (\beta_H + \beta_{HPh} - \beta_{H_2Ph})$.

Plots of L.H.S. of equation (10) against μ at all the temperatures were linear, the intercepts of which at $\mu=0$ gave $\log K_1$ and the slopes gave β_1 . The values of pK_1 thus found have been recorded in Table 2.

It will be seen that the values of pK_1 and pK_2 obtained with different series at all the temperatures closely agree among themselves and with the values reported by the original workers. Only at 298.15 K the difference in pK_1 goes upto 0.006 and that in pK_2 upto 0.007. The linear plots and the constancy of β_1 and β_2 for different series of solutions confirm the assumption that β_1 and β_2 are independent of the composition of ionic atmosphere.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. B. Prasad for his interest and to the U.G.C., New Delhi for a Teacher Fellowship under faculty improvement programme to one of them (A.K.S.).

References

1. B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 588.
2. C. W. DAVIES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, **140**, 2093.
3. W. J. HAMER, G. D. PINCHING and S. F. ACREE, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1945, **35**, 589.
4. W. J. HAMER and S. F. ACREE, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1945, **35**, 381.
5. W. J. HAMER and S. F. ACREE, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1944, **33**, 87.
6. H. S. HARNED and R. W. EHLERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 2179.
7. G. G. MANOV, R. G. BATES, W. J. HAMER and S. F. ACREE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1765.
8. R. G. BATES, "Electrometric pH Determination", Wiley, New York, 1954, p. 318.
9. A. K. SINHA, J. C. GHOSH and B. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 586.

Mechanism of Ruthenium(III) Catalysed Oxidation of 4-Aminobutyric Acid by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III) Ions

BHARAT SINGH*, ASHOK KUMAR SINGH
and

JITENDRA PRATAP SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211 002

Manuscript received 12 June 1980, revised 10 November 1982,
accepted 20 May 1983

USE of catalytic amount of ruthenium(III) chloride^{1,2} prompted us to investigate the kinetics and mechanism of ruthenium(III) catalysed oxidation of 4-aminobutyric acid by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) ions. The results show zero-order dependence on [hexacyanoferrate(III)] and first-order on both [Ru(III)] and [OH⁻]. First order dependence on lower [4-aminobutyric acid] tends to zero-order at higher concentrations. A suitable

mechanism involving formation of a transient complex between Ru(III) and substrate has been proposed.

Experimental

The solution of ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) was prepared by dissolving the sample in hydrochloric acid of known strength. All other reagents used were of AR grade except 4-aminobutyric acid (Fluka), sodium perchlorate (Riedel) and ferroin indicator (E. Merck).

The reaction was followed by quenching the reaction mixture in H₂SO₄ and estimating the ferrocyanide formed volumetrically against standard ceric sulphate solution.

Results and Discussion

Variation of hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration shows zero-order dependence on [hexacyanoferrate(III)]. The rate of oxidation follows first-order kinetics with respect to [4-aminobutyric acid] at lower concentrations of 4-ABA and tends to zero-order at higher concentrations. The reaction rate is directly proportional to the [ruthenium(III) chloride] showing first-order dependence on [Ru(III)]. The reaction rate increases with increasing [OH⁻] and is also first-order in [OH⁻].

The reactions were carried out in the temperature range 25-45° (Table 1) and the value of ΔE^\ddagger calculated from the Arrhenius plot is 18.4 ± 0.2 k cal mole⁻¹. Positive effect of ionic strength of the medium on reaction rate was observed.

It is well known that amino acids exist as zwitter ions in aqueous solution and dissociate to amino acid anions. The pK values for

systems are reported³ to be ~ 9.60 (at 25°). Since the pH of the reaction mixture is >10, the anion of 4-aminobutyric acid is assumed to be the reactive species. Ruthenium(III) chloride exists as [Ru(H₂O)₆]³⁺ in dilute hydrochloric acid⁴. Such type of aquo-complexes are known to exist in the form [Ru(H₂O)₆OH]²⁺ in equilibrium⁵ with hexa-aquo form.

In alkaline medium, the dissociation (1) would be highly favoured, suggesting that [Ru(H₂O)₅OH]²⁺ is the real reactive species of ruthenium(III) chloride in alkaline medium.

On the basis of the above facts the following scheme of oxidation is proposed where S stands for 4-aminobutyric acid and Ru(III) has been written in place of the reactive species of ruthenium(III) chloride for the sake of simplicity.

* Author for correspondence.